

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Seedling root dip treatments to control gall midge (GM)

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We sought to develop a simple, economic method for GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) control. In 1982 kharif we evaluated 8 chlorpyrifos 0.02% treatments for GM control (see table). Unprotected Jaya seedlings (5.3% silvershoots were recorded in the nursery) were planted in a

replicated trial in 5- × 5-m plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. For the seedling root treatment, rock phosphate at 60 kg P/ha was mixed with wet clay at 3:1 and water was added to make a thick slurry. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC was mixed with the slurry at 0.02% concentration. Seedling roots were uniformly coated with the chlorpyrifos-treated slurry and planted. At planting, the field was puddled with very little standing water.

Because seedlings were GM infested at planting, all treatments had GM incidence even at 15 d after transplanting (DT).

However, incidence increased significantly only in the untreated control up to 45 DT. Beyond 60 DT there was no significant difference in GM infestation between treatments, largely because GM-infested seedlings were planted. Preinfestation treatment is essential. As an alternative to chlorpyrifos seedling root dip for 12 or 3 h, chlorpyrifos-treated carbon phosphate treatments gave good results (see table). Carbon phosphate is commonly used in rice and coconut soils at Goa in kharif. □

Effect of seedling root dip treatments on GM damage and rice grain yield, Goa, India, 1982.^a

Treatment	Silvershoots (%)				Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Gross profit ^b (\$/ha)	Cost of insecticide application ^c (\$/ha)	Net gain ^d (\$/ha)	Gain from insecticide ^e (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ^f
	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT							
SRD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h	3.8 a	2.5 ab	11.4 ab	19.3a	6.4 a	3.4 a	438	6	432	210	36.0
SRD with chlorpyrifos 0.02% in 1% urea solution for 3 h	6.9 a	1.9 a	8.9 a	25.5 a	5.9 a	2.4 b	319	7	312	90	13.9
SRT with chlorpyrifos 0.02% treated CPS for											
1 min	5.7 a	8.0 c	19.7 c	26.1 a	6.1 a	2.2 b	285	6	279	57	10.5
5 min	3.3 a	7.1 c	18.4 bc	30.1 a	5.5 a	2.1 b	272	6	266	44	8.3
10 min	7.1 a	5.1 bc	15.8 ab	34.0 a	5.5 a	2.3 b	296	6	290	68	12.3
20 min	5.3 a	7.5 c	16.8 bc	26.2 a	5.4 a	2.4 b	319	6	313	91	16.2
30 min	3.5 a	5.5 bc	16.6 bc	26.8 a	5.0 a	2.3 b	300	6	294	72	13.0
Untreated control	5.6 a	20.2 d	32.6 d	27.9 a	4.8 a	1.7 b	222	0	222	—	—

^a Mean of 3 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. SRD = seedling root dip, SRT = seedling root treatment, CPS = carbon phosphate slurry, DT = days after transplanting. ^b Yield in kg/ha at 14% moisture × \$0.13. ^c \$1.31 for labor + cost of insecticide including the cost of urea. ^d Gross profit – cost of insecticide application. ^e Net gain of treatment – net gain of control. ^f (Gross profit of treatment – gross profit of control) ÷ cost of insecticide application.

Tyrophagus palmarum (Oudemans) mite in rice seedlings and leaf sheaths

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The mite *T. palmarum* (Oudemans) (Acaridae: Astigmata) was recorded to infest rice in China. In India, the first recorded mite infestation was observed in rice seedlings and leaf sheaths of Ratna in a 1977 rabi nursery at CRRI. Mite infestations were surveyed in rice nurseries and fields in 1979 and 1982-84.

The mite infested seedlings and leaf sheaths of Ratna, Karuna, CR1009, CR1014, Jaya, Vijaya, Pusa 2-21, Kalinga-I, Supriya, and Jagannath (see table). It was identified at the United States Department of Agriculture Systematic Entomology Department.

Adults and nymphs feed on growing leaves of seedlings, causing a bleached appearance followed by wilting, shriveling, and drying. These symptoms were confirmed by inoculating adult mites on 10-d-old Ratna seedlings and observing mite development under controlled conditions. Inoculating 10

or 100 mites/100 seedlings produced similar symptoms after 15 d. Mite populations varied from 2 to 34 mites/seedling (see table) on 25-d-old seedlings from 1983 dry and wet season nurseries. Mites were counted using a stereoscopic binocular microscope.

T. palmarum has more hairs than most rice-infesting mites. The post-abdominal region has five pair of hairs as long as or longer than the mite's legs. Two pair of hair grow on each side of the anterior abdominal region between the 2d and 3d pair of legs (see figure). The mite is transparent but takes on the